

Vitrification and upcycling of inorganic waste

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ABSTRACT

The vitrification of wastes is in general accepted as a reliable way to stabilize dangerous and hazardous wastes in the form of glass. One of the world's most complex vitrification projects, the Hanford Waste treatment and immobilization plant (USA) [1], was launched as a response to, what was up until very recently, the most severe nuclear pollution in the Western hemisphere. This clean-up project has gathered tremendous amounts of data on how to turn the radioactive and toxic nuclear waste into a stable glass. This waste is in the form of slurries, which contain over 60 elements, and are stored in 177 underground tanks. Each tank needs to be treated separately, the suitable glass forming and modifying additives need to be tailored to their unique composition and only then can the slurry be vitrified. After long years of research, the Hanford area clean-up will be finally launched in 2022 [2].

This particular issue of nuclear pollution could be perceived as non-relatable in Europe, where in general the vitrification of nuclear fission byproducts is the subject of well-working technology. However, with growing consumer demand, and the ever growing industrial production, the issue of environmental pollution is becoming a grievous global issue of the 21st century [3]–[7]. The recycling of used materials is no longer sufficient, and in recent years it has also failed in many areas. The most significant area is the failure to process chemical variations of the same material (i.e. plastics), or to even address potential recycling of composite materials. The best example would be solar collectors, where vast numbers of them will be obsolete in the next few decades. That will add just another item to the ever-growing list of inorganic and partially inorganic waste streams, which already include waste from the glass making industry (glass shards, cutting debris, insulations), mining sites (byproducts from ore), ashes from incineration sites, TV screens, medical waste etc. [3].

Another setback of recycling is that it demands proper separation of the waste for the desired recycling stream, and leaves behind a significant share of final waste that ends in landfills, which are rapidly growing in price [8]. This is one of the main reasons why governments and industry are very reluctant to invest more into this technology, which only gets a marginally positive net balance against the full-landfill solution.

Hanford's ability to turn waste streams into stable glass could be the inspiration for the launch of inorganic vitrification projects in Europe and worldwide. The vitrification could provide a solution to toxic, stable and obsolete materials, which do not have alternative solutions nowadays. However, if the aim of the vitrification would only be the reduction of waste volume via the waste glass designated for landfill, due to expenses, there would only be a little motivation on the market economy to actually participate [9].

Therefore, the aim for the inorganic waste vitrification should not be the production of waste glasses, but of the products that would re-enter market as novel and attractive materials. For example, if a consolidated vitrification product enters flame synthesis, it could result in the formation of glasses with novel composition and applications. One such application could be in the popular, and growing, 3D printing technology (AMT-Additive Manufacturing Technology). Another possibility is the design and manufacturing of building materials from insulations to construction parts that would bring longer durability, better mechanical properties or would replace decoration materials, i.e. marble, which nowadays comes at the cost of the destruction of natural sites [4].

However, in the first step, there needs to be a cooperation with industry partners from the

mid-European area, and also with the research institutions in that area. A library of partner sites is currently built with information on waste type and volume and then from the obtained samples, the general composition for particular waste streams (i.e. via XRF, SEM-EDS/WDS, XRD) will be added as well. In the second step, after the example of the Hanford project, target glasses would be designed for a particular purpose and could also open the door to the idea of recycling-upcycling in the research of novel materials and composites for targeted applications with better chemical, physical and mechanical properties than existing materials.

Keywords: Recycling, Upcycling, Waste management, Vitrification, Flame synthesis, AMT, Foam glass.

Acknowledgment:

This paper is a part of dissemination activities of project [FunGlass](#). This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation program under grant agreement No 739566.

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